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ENDORSEMENT BY THE DEAN

This is to certify that the dissertation entitled "ASSOCIATION BETWEEN ALTERED THORACIC ROTATION MOVEMENT IN SUBJECTS WITH AND WITHOUT NONSPECIFIC LOW BACK PAIN -A CASE CONTROL STUDY" is a bonafide research work done by AJANYA N K under the guidance of DEAN PROF. Dr. S RAJASEKAR Srinivas University, College of Physiotherapy, Mangalore, Karnataka.

Date: 17/8/21

Place: Mangalore

Signature:

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This is to certify that the dissertation entitled “Normative Data for median and ulnar nerve conduction and F – wave response among healthy individuals of Mangalore, Karnataka” is a bonafide research work done by **HARSH NAINWANI** under the guidance of **Dr. Thrishala Noronha, Assistant Professor, Srinivas University, College of Physiotherapy, Mangalore, Karnataka.**

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This is to certify that the dissertation entitled "INDIVIDUAL AGE SPECIFIC NORMATIVE DATA AND REFERENCE EQUATION FOR INCREMENTAL SHUTTLE WALK TEST IN HEALTHY CHILDREN AGED BETWEEN 5-12 YEARS" is a bonafide research work done by MAGHNA.E the guidance of Dr. JEYAGANESH VELLAISAMY Assistant Professor, Srinivas University, College of Physiotherapy, Mangalore, Karnataka.

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This is to certify that the dissertation entitled “**EFFECTIVENESS OF YOGA IN ADDITION TO PHYSIOTHERAPY TO IMPROVE ATTENTION AND FUNCTIONAL IMPAIRMENT IN CHILDREN WITH CEREBRAL PALSY: A RANDOMISED CLINICAL TRIAL**” is a Bonafide research work done by **VARSHA K** under the guidance of **Dr. RADHIKA GOPAL S, Assistant Professor**, Srinivas University, College of Physiotherapy, Mangaluru, Karnataka.

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